

THE INTERNET ADDICTION: CHALLENGES TO CONFLICT SETTLEMENT IN FAMILY COMMUNICATION

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ABSTRAK

The internet has been interfering with human's life in every aspect, the family communication's including. The way a family communicate nowadays has been changing in almost decade along the emerge of the digital era. It is known that the use of digital tools of communication in children also is improving from times to times. Parents themselves are different today; some must do the adaptation and most of them are very habitually used to these tools of communication. These circumstances towards addiction of internet use are the vantage point of this paper and become research's focus. The objective of this research is to describe the changes of family communication afterward internet incoming in conflict settlement. Research method used in this research is a qualitative study with observational approach. Research's result retorts how family communication meets some significant changes involving conflict and settlement toward members of the family.

Keywords: Internet Addiction, Family Communication Conflict Settlement.

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